

Assessment of the results of the National Residue Control Plan 2009 and the residue control plan for third-country imports 2009

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The National Residue Control Plan (NRKP) is a programme of measures that monitor foodstuffs of animal origin at different levels of production in regard to residues of undesirable substances. The residue control plan for third-country imports (ERKP) monitors animal products from third-countries for residues of undesirable substances.

In many cases, maximum limits are defined for residues and contaminants that may not be exceeded in foodstuffs of animal origin. The aim of the control of foodstuffs within the NRKP and ERKP programme is to assess compliance with these maximum limits, to reveal the illegal use of banned or unauthorised substances as well as to determine the origin of residue contamination.

The Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety (BVL) has provided the results of samples analysed by the federal control authorities in 2009. Only 0.45 % of the samples exceeded maximum limits or contained residues of unauthorised substances. The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has carried out a health assessment of these samples and concluded that the one-time or occasional intake of foods containing the residues found does not constitute a health risk for the consumer.

The full version of this BfR Opinion is available in German on http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/208/bewertung_der_ergebnisse_des_nationalen_rueckstandskontrollplans_2009_und_des_einfuhrrueckstandskontrollplans_2009.pdf